

Case studies and validation

- Diagnosis of fever without an apparent source and differentiation between viral and bacterial infections

- Early warning systems for HAB (Harmful Algal Blooms)

contact.

multilab-project.eu

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multilab

Multi-modal, configurable
optical lab-on-chip
platform for low-cost
multipurpose diagnostics
& monitoring

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Sensor platform

- SiN PIC platform with CMOS compatible plasmonic structures and sensing modules deployed interchangeably based on application needs
- Cost-efficient manufacturing process
- Combination with customised microfluidics structures to speed-up measurement while enhancing LOD

Sensing modules

- On-chip PTS for extending, sensing capabilities to the mid-IR region for direct, label-free and reagent-free multi-component analysis
- Graphite-based ECL sensors to detect additional inorganic species (dissolved O₂, H₂S) and enzyme-based biomarkers (lactic and uric acids)
- PA-AWG sensor for multichannel, simultaneous sensing of various proteins, miRNA and pathogens

Novel instruments exploiting the PIC

- Cost-effective readout system, compatible with all sensing modules on the PIC
- Two instrument versions

PROTOTYPE A:

For medical use case with single-use PICs

PROTOTYPE B:

For fully autonomous long-term environmental sensing with reusable PICs

PA-AWG: Plasmonic Augmented - Arrayed Waveguide Grating

PTS: Photothermal Spectrometry

ECL: Electrochemiluminescence

PIC: Photonic Integrated Circuit